

Studying text recognition using data mining methods

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Abstract

Text recognition is a method for recognizing text from a file in the desired format (such as .doc or .txt). Several steps are included in this process, like pre-processing, segmentation, feature extraction, classification, and post-processing. The pre-processing is done as a binarized picture to convert a greyscale image, and noise is decreased on the input image of the basic operation by eliminating the image signal noise. The segmentation phase is used to segment the online image and each character of the segmentation line. The purpose of feature extraction is to calculate the properties of an image document. This page outlines ways for transforming a paper document's textual content into a machine-readable format. This research examines and compares the technological problems, methodologies, and performance of text detection and identification investigations in colour photographs.

Text-Mining can be called data mining, refers to a process of extracting non-trivial patterns from an unstructured document that contains text. It can be visualized or known as an extension of data mining from a structured database

Introduction

Text recognition can be known as optical character recognition. Many applications rely on text recognition, including language translation, identity verification, language translation etc. It is necessary to understand that in text in image contains high-level semantic information. The number of images on the internet and in databases is growing. In the we use text mining, is a multidisciplinary field, involving information retrieval, text analysis information clustering, extraction, categorization, visualizing databases, data mining and machine learning. Text Mining can be visualized as Text Refining that transforms free form of text document into a particular form or a particular pattern

Figure 1.0

In figure 1.0: A framework for text mining. Text refining is the process of converting unstructured text content into an intermediate form (IF). IF can be either document- or concept-based. A document-based IF's knowledge distillation deduces patterns or knowledge across texts. By extracting object information relevant to a domain, a document-based IF may be projected onto a concept-based IF.

A concept-based IF's knowledge distillation deduces patterns or information across objects or ideas.

Machine Learning Technique Used:

1. Linear Regression
2. Logistic Regression
3. Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA)
4. Multivariate Adaptive Regression splines

Instance Based Algorithms

1. K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN)

S.No.	Algorithm	Merits	Demerits
Regression algorithms			
1	Linear Regression	Space complexity is very low it just needs to save the weights at the end of training. Hence it's a high latency algorithm. It's very simple to understand Good interpretability Feature importance is generated at the time model building.	The algorithm assumes data is normally distributed in real they are not. Before building model multicollinearity should be avoided. prone to outliers
2	Logistic Regression	It is more robust: the independent variables don't have to be normally distributed, or have equal variance in each group. It may handle nonlinear effects	It can't solve non-linear problems with logistic regression since it's decision surface is linear. Prone to overfitting
3	Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA)	The solid underlying theory, stable estimation of time-varying trends and seasonal patterns, relatively few parameters.	No explicit seasonal indices, hard to interpret coefficients, the danger of overfitting or misidentification if not used with care.
4	Multivariate Adaptive Regression Splines	Works well even with a large number of predictor variables Automatically detects interactions between variables Efficient and fast Robust to outliers	Difficult to understand Prone to overfitting Model is vulnerable to missing data
Instance-based algorithms			
5	K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN)	The simple technique that is easily implemented Building model is cheap An extremely flexible classification scheme Well suited for Multi-	Classifying unknown records are relatively expensive. Accuracy can be severely degraded by the presence of

2.

Linear Regression: Linear Regression can be used in text recognition as a feature extraction approach for example Optical Character Recognition (OCR) to compute features such as horizontal and vertical

profiles which lead to the distribution of pixel intensities along rows and columns of an image. These characteristics can then be fed into a classifier or recognition system.

Logistic Regression: Logistic regression is a basic yet effective text recognition technique, especially in binary or multiclass classification contexts. It makes predictions or categorises based on the link between textual characteristics and target classifications. More sophisticated methods, like as deep learning models, may be used to capture detailed patterns and relationships within text data for more complicated text recognition jobs or when working with large-scale datasets.

Or you can refer to the figure 1.1

Conclusion:

This article provides an overview of several text recognition approaches, strategies, and recognition algorithms. The accuracy of various text recognition algorithms is examined based on a survey of the literature. The full processes and flow of text recognition approaches surveyed from numerous research publications, including image capture, pre-processing, feature extraction, classification, and post-processing. Text's advantages and disadvantages